

Safely integrating crew aviation and unmanned aviation in the polish sky

Katarzyna Kostur, PhD., lecturer at Polish Airforce University, Dęblin, Poland, kosturkatarzyna@gmail.com , ORCID: 0000-0002-2552-6709;

Malgorzata Zmigrodzka, PhD., assistant professor at Polish Airforce University, Dęblin, Poland, malgorzatazmigordzka@gmail.com , ORCID: 0000-0003-3896-0819;

Tomasz Balcerzak, Ph.D., assistant professor in the Institute of Air and Space Law, Faculty of Law and Administration, Lazarski University in Warsaw, Poland, tomasz.balcerzak@lazarski.pl, ORCID: 0000-0002-3845-998X;

Andrzej Fellner, Prof. Silesian University of Technology, afellner@o2.pl, ORCID: 0000-0001-5634-5516

Piotr Uchroński, Prof. WSB University, Dabrowa Gornicza, uchronski.p@gmail.com , ORCID: 0000-0002-0127-8026.

Abstract:

In Poland, we are dealing with a huge development of the drone market. The pandemic has only accelerated the use of new technologies. The number of certified professional drone pilots has long since increased to over 25,000. Therefore, it is important to develop solutions that will allow for the stable, sustainable and safe development of the UAV market and its applications in various parts of the country. One of such solutions is the DTM Autonomia system, which enables the implementation of state-of-the-art drone flights in large numbers and over long distances. The aim of the article is to highlight the process of safe integration of manned and unmanned aviation through a system supporting state-of-the-art drone flights in large numbers and over long distances. Of course, the research process analyzed the most important problems related to the integration of manned aviation with unmanned systems. The article presents significant research on social acceptance of planned changes in the airspace.

KEY WORDS: system, safety, drones, DTM, UTM

Streszczenie:

W Polsce mamy do czynienia z ogromnym rozwojem rynku dronów. Pandemia tylko przyspieszyła wykorzystanie nowych technologii. Liczba certyfikowanych zawodowych pilotów dronów już dawno wzrosła do ponad 25 000. Dlatego ważne jest wypracowanie rozwiązań, które pozwolą na stabilny, zrównoważony i bezpieczny rozwój rynku BSP i jego zastosowań w różnych częściach kraju. Jednym z takich rozwiązań jest system DTM Autonomia, który umożliwia realizację najnowocześniejszych lotów dronami w dużych ilościach i na duże odległości. Celem artykułu jest zwrócenie uwagi na proces bezpiecznej integracji lotnictwa załogowego i bezzałogowego poprzez system wspierania nowoczesnych lotów dronów w dużych ilościach i na duże odległości. Oczywiście w procesie badawczym przeanalizowano najważniejsze problemy związane z integracją lotnictwa załogowego z systemami bezzałogowymi. W artykule przedstawiono istotne badania dotyczące akceptacji społecznej planowanych zmian w przestrzeni powietrznej.

Słowa kluczowe: system, bezpieczeństwo, drony, DTM, UTM

1. Introduction

Poland is a stakeholder of the U-space concept – a space in which remote controlled, automatic and future autonomous platforms can operate safely. It is possible because of precision air traffic management. At EU level, U-space involves the creation of a regulatory framework that will allow the increased drone traffic to be handled efficiently and safely. The market for civilian drones is dominated by drones operated by the operator, i.e. the pilot. The need for long-range and off-sight operations requires progress in the implementation of U-space. This will also require the development of a technological infrastructure to ensure the safe management and monitoring of such operations. Implementing Regulation (EU) 2019/947 of 24 May 2019 on rules and procedures for the operation of unmanned aircraft clearly sets out the principles for the unification of rules for the safe operation of drones and the opening of borders within the EU.

The current trend to minimize costs while ensuring high standards, efficiency and reducing negative environmental impacts is accelerating the uptake of the new and innovative technologies. Drones do not need a crew on board during the flight. They can be remotely controlled or automatically flown. According to the report “Application of services provided unmanned aerial vehicles (GNP services) developed under the auspices of the Ministry of Enterprise and Technology in 2018 to increase the efficiency and quality of the delivery of public services by local authorities”, the PNB market is developing very dynamically and would be soon take the one of the most important segments of the economy (Stanley M., 2019).

Integrating crewed aviation and unmanned aviation (such as “drones”) in the Polish airspace involves a multifaceted approach to consider for safe integration. For example

Poland, as part of the European Union, must adhere to the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) regulations. EASA provides guidelines and regulations for the operation of unmanned aircraft systems (UAS), which Poland would need to incorporate into its national regulations. These regulations cover aspects like operator certification, drone registration, and operational limitations. The second important aspect is Air Traffic Management (ATM): Modifying existing ATM systems to accommodate unmanned aircraft. This include the development of U-space, a set of new services and procedures designed to support safe, efficient, and secure access to airspace for large numbers of drones. Another important think is implementing technologies like detect-and-avoid systems for drones can mitigate the risk of collisions with crewed aircraft. This technology is analogous to the 'see-and-avoid' principle in crewed aviation and is crucial for maintaining safe distances.

The training for both drone operators and crewed aircraft pilots on how to safely share airspace is essential. This training should include awareness of each other's operational limitations and capabilities.

Very big problem is public awareness and education. The Public education campaigns are informing people about safe drone operation and the regulations that must be followed. This can reduce instances of unauthorized or unsafe drone operations.

Obviously, collaboration with other countries and international bodies can aid in adopting best practices and harmonizing regulations and standards for unmanned aviation. By addressing these aspects, Poland can effectively and safely integrate crewed and unmanned aviation in its airspace, fostering innovation while maintaining safety standards.

2. Urbanized areas as one of the determinants of introducing drones as courier parcels

The pace of urbanization development and the growth of the population create the need for cooperation with new technologies. Part of the problem is urban delivery and demand for this is likely to increase as e-commerce volumes grow. According to insurance company Swiss Re, the global urban population "... will increase by about 1.4 billion to 5 billion between 2011 and 2030, with a 90% increase in emerging markets ..." (Automation and innovations in logistic processes of electronic commerce). This data mobilizes the market to look for ideas to unload congested cities and use drones to deliver parcels. Courier deliveries in different countries are tested. The result of the delivered deliveries via the first intelligent route is the reduction of time from 40 to 8 minutes and a significant reduction in transport costs, with lower CO2 emissions and energy consumption. Various companies, small and large, compete in the field of cargo and courier services, embarking on various projects and tests. These works indicated

many directions and opportunities for development, for example the supply of blood or organs using unmanned aerial vehicles. Unfortunately, technological possibilities alone are not enough, and at the same time, society must be prepared and educated in the field of airspace use (Cobel-Tokarska, 2011).

Automation and innovative solutions are the dominant trend. Companies operating in Western Europe have been investing for years and successfully applying modern solutions in these areas, and Poland is definitely opening up in this direction (Feltynowski M. 2019).

In the field of public safety, unmanned aerial platforms are used for:

- patrolling more important communication routes in cities, on expressways, highways, access roads to cities in order to provide information about congestion, accidents and other dangerous situations
- monitoring the course of rescue operations at places of catastrophes and natural disasters
- use of properly equipped UAVs for border patrolling
- monitoring and co-ordination information during chases
- monitoring the course of mass events in terms of the organization of security and public order,
- monitoring selected particularly dangerous areas of cities and providing information on committed crimes, offenses, acts of vandalism and the perpetrators of these acts,
- use of monitoring systems in operational activities, inspection of dangerous places or objects, non-invasive conduct of process activities at event sites,
- transporting and discharging chemical incapacitating agents, spikes for stopping vehicles, means of simulating the battlefield,
- search for people in hiding and missing persons.

Drones are common in many areas of life, such as: reconnaissance, surveillance, collecting data about the target, making digital maps, monitoring targets, supporting search and rescue missions both in peacetime (SAR) and in conflict (CSAR) (including in "Żwirko i Wigura", 2020).

In such difficult situations as the COVID 19 pandemic. As a result of the rapid spread of this type of disease, all available countermeasures are important, as well as those to protect and patrol critical infrastructure, i.e. airports and seaports. These places are the most threatened and most frequented by citizens from all over the world. The use of drones in this case is very justified and safe, especially in certain areas such as:

- environmental monitoring of water and air,
- monitoring of security threats,
- verification of emergency reports,
- monitoring of the composition of bulk materials,
- operational support during protests, eg of dissatisfied population
- support in Search & Rescue operations within the administrative port area,

- operational support in the event of environmental contamination,
- delivery of rescue or medical supplies to port.

The drone industry of various types, both terrestrial and airborne, has found a very effective application during a pandemic, including: to announce notifications about not leaving homes, to measure body temperature, thanks to the installed thermal cameras, they are able to catch people with fever from the crowd, as well as to checking the presence of people during quarantine, delivering packages with medical supplies and food. The crisis situation in the world related to the epidemic is a significant signal to learn to cooperate with new technologies (Xiao-Guang Y., Teng L., Shanhai G., Rountree E., Chao-Yang W., 2021).

3. U-Space - the concept of safe integration of manned and unmanned aviation

The U-Space concept assumes the safe and effective integration of manned and unmanned aviation. Poland is currently the leader in the preparations of the U-Space environment among the member states of the Single European Sky (SES) initiative (Swiss Re's latest sigma study). The drone industry is growing at a rate of almost 50 percent. annually, that's why one of the main goals of PANSAs in the field of unmanned aerial vehicles are activities supporting the creation of a friendly environment in Poland for the further development of the UAV services market, i.e. the implementation of the U-space concept, assuming the safe and effective integration of manned and unmanned aviation (Feltynowski M. 2019). Achieving the integration of drones will be an iterative process: as more services are deployed and operations are enabled, drones will be progressively integrated into all classes of airspace until reaching a point where full integration is achieved. Throughout this process, manned and unmanned aviation will develop, with each sector benefitting from the technologies and evolutions of the other (Guillermet F. 2018).

4. Pansa UTM

PANSA UTM (Unmanned Traffic Management) refers to a system developed by the Polish Air Navigation Services Agency (PANSA) for managing the traffic of unmanned aerial systems (UAS), commonly known as drones. This system is designed to ensure safe and efficient integration of drone operations into the national airspace.

Pansa UTM - digital concept of UAV flight coordination and digital management of applications and consents for flights in the airspace, which consists of PANSA's proprietary operational solutions and a system part, integrated with the Droneradar mobile application, the most popular among drone operators in Poland. Out of 16 U-Space services, as many as nine have already been successfully implemented despite the 5-year transition period. The so-called

Urban Air Mobility (AMU), which covers the issues of technology, through regulations, social acceptance, air traffic management, to physical infrastructure, is supported by the NaviSpot center, which builds a strong base for the development of Polish drone technologies based on digitization. The key elements of U-space are, among others Unmanned Traffic Management and Drone Traffic Management systems (PansaUTM).

The system has functionalities that allow BSP operators to, among other things, notify planned flights, verify the feasibility of a flight in terms of compliance with current legislation and airspace availability, and receive digital approvals (where required). The ANSP DTM (Pansa UTM subsystem) has an interface for air traffic services, which will be used, inter alia, in the controlled space around the main national airports and will enable tactical non-verbal electronic communication between air traffic controllers and PANSA information officers and BSP operators (Balcerzak T.2017).

Fig.1 Dronradar
 Source: <https://www.pansa.pl/u-space/>, access: 15.06.2024.

It is necessary to carefully consider all issues related to the problems and requirements for determining routes and their parameters and running specific types of DTMs. We need to consider the issue of DTMs intersecting and drones from other operators flying through them, issues of time slots, connection with the ground, avoiding obstacles, determining the altitude or frequency of routes(Balcerzak T.2016).

The system is divided into two basic modules. The first concerns the management of applications for BSP flights in the PANSAs area of responsibility. Here, requests can be analyzed and preliminary approvals for BSP flights can be issued, along with the conditions for such flights. The second module is the direct contact of the BSP operator with the ATS services of the PANSAs before take-off, based on the pre-approved BSP flight. If everything agrees, a go-ahead is issued; if the operational situation does not allow such a flight to take off, PANSAs services may reject such a flight or modify its parameters. So navigation system generally are ready for using but taking into account the entire catalogue of risks arising from the misuse of drones by unauthorized persons or entities, anti-drone system technology should be implemented in institutions responsible for the security of citizens (Aomar, H., Bentley, P.J,2021).

Another problem is 5G technology, which is essential to ensure total availability, enabling the mass deployment of the Internet of Things (IoT), i.e. being able to support millions of devices in urban areas, while offering acceptable levels of energy consumption, equipment cost and network deployment and operation costs.

The question of the risks posed by the use of drones for civilian purposes in the service of protecting public safety is an important one. The devices with which drones are equipped as standard and those that may be their add-on components carry the risk of being used to interfere with the private lives of citizens(Balcerzak T., Fellner R.,2016). Non-governmental organizations concerned with the protection of citizens' rights and freedoms point out that the positive social effects that can be more easily achieved with drones will actually occur provided that drones are used by public services in the right way and for the right purpose (Niklas J., Walkowiak A. 2014).

Figure 3. DTM and UTM integration

Source: <https://www.pansa.pl/en/pansautm/> , access: 15.06.2024.

It is necessary to determine what rules of cooperation will apply between the DTM operator and PANSATM. PANSATM must be able to ground drones or influence traffic in DTM, e.g. due to an medical flight. We should specify what information must be processed from the drone to DTM and then to UTM. The method of transferring responsibility when leaving the DTM, system intervention, flight route approval, and the minimum time and scope of readiness to respond to a command from the UTM should be determined.

It is necessary to carefully consider all issues related to the problems and requirements for determining routes and their parameters and running specific types of DTMs. We need to consider the issue of DTMs intersecting and drones from other operators flying through them, issues of time slots, connection with the ground, avoiding obstacles, determining the altitude or frequency of routes(Balcerzak T,2014).

4. Social factors

Considering the integration of manned and unmanned aviation, it is important, in addition to technological capabilities, to know the needs and awareness of the public. To this end, a survey was carried out on the territory of the Polish Republic, including stakeholders in the aviation sector, in particular: passengers, customers-customers of the new concept, employers producing, using new flight concepts, aircraft crews and air traffic service personnel (Żmigrodzka M., 2022).

The research results presented here are from a project carried out for the "Sector Competence Council of the aerospace industry", which is part of the Operational Program Knowledge Education Development, Measure 2.12 Increasing knowledge of qualification and professional needs with funding from the European Social Fund.

The data collected in the research process made it possible to find out the opinions of aviation stakeholders and, based on them, identify those factors that can have a significant impact on the development of the concept of flying unmanned aircraft or with a single pilot on board in commercial passenger and cargo transport.

The survey included subjects, professional groups: flying personnel (pilots, cabin crew and support staff),air traffic controllers (air and ground), operations personnel, technical personnel, ground handling personnel, flight safety service personnel, others identified.

Respondents were asked to rank the identified social factors that will contribute to the popularization of commercial passenger and cargo (cargo) flights without the presence of a pilot - in order of importance.

The largest number of respondents (46%) indicated passenger interest as the most important social factor contributing to the popularization of commercial passenger and cargo

(cargo)flights without the presence of a pilot. In second place was the organization of flights - 31%. Ecology | (first choice - 4%, last choice - 42%) and opinions of professional groups (first choice - 4%, last choice - 35%) were indicated as the least important factors.

Survey

1. During the survey, respondents were asked the following questions:

Fig 4. Interest in unmanned flights
Source: authors study

58% of respondents believe that commercial passenger flights without pilots on board will reduce interest in such flights. 8% of respondents hold the opposite view. 34% of respondents indicated that the absence of pilots on board will not affect passenger interest in such flights.

Fig. 5. Opinions of social groups in the aviation sector on unmanned flights
Source: authors study

As many as 88% of those surveyed felt that commercial passenger flights without pilots on board would arouse dissatisfaction and protests from professional groups or other aviation-related circles. 4% of respondents indicated that they would improve working conditions and increase satisfaction, while 8% felt that they would not affect the opinions of aviation professional groups or other aviation-related circles.

Fig. 6. Impact of unmanned flights on employment
 Source: authors study.

31% of respondents said they would increase employment. 46% of respondents take the opposite view. 11% of respondents believe they will not increase employment, and 12% believe they will have no impact on employment.

Fig.7. Impact of unmanned flights on flight organization
 Source: authors study.

42% of respondents indicated that commercial passenger flights without pilots on board would improve flight conditions and service. The opposite view is held by 39% of respondents. 19% of respondents are of the opinion that commercial passenger flights without pilots on board will have no impact on flight organization.

Fig.8. Environmental impact of unmanned flights
 Source: authors study.

The majority of respondents - 65% - indicated that commercial passenger flights without pilots on board will not affect the environment. 27% of respondents believe that they will not reduce the environmental impact of flights, and 8% believe that they will reduce the environmental impact of flights.

Fig. 9. Impact of single pilot participation on flight interest
 Source: authors study.

According to 58% of respondents, single-pilot commercial passenger flights will not affect passenger interest in such flights. 34% of respondents, on the other hand, believe that they will reduce interest in such flights, while 8% hold the opposite view.

Fig. 10. Impact of single-pilot flight on flight organization

Source: authors study.

Forty-two percent of respondents said they would worsen flight conditions and passenger service or have no impact on flight arrangements. 16% of respondents believe they will improve flight conditions and passenger service.

Fig. 11. The impact of unmanned flights on demand

Source: authors study.

65% of respondents believe that air freight (cargo) without pilots on board will not affect demand. In contrast, 27% of respondents believe that demand will increase. The opposite view is held by 8% of respondents.

Fig.12. The impact of unmanned flights on the opinions of professional groups

Source: authors study.

77% of respondents believe that such measures will arouse dissatisfaction and protests from aviation professional groups and other aviation-related circles. 12% believe they will not be

affected, while 11% believe they will improve working conditions and increase satisfaction.

Fig. 13 Impact of unmanned cargo flights on flight organization

Source: authors study.

42% of respondents answered that these flights will have no impact. In contrast, 35% of respondents believe that such measures will improve the clearance of goods. 9% of respondents take the opposite view. In contrast, 8% indicate that such measures will worsen the clearance of goods.

Survey findings - social factor

Taking into account the results of the survey conducted by the research team, a major influence on the social acceptance of changes in air transport is the interest of passengers, followed by the organization of flights, the opinions of professional groups, of course, employment issues, but more emphasis on this factor is placed by specific professional groups no and ecology, which, according to respondents, has the least impact on changes in the reduction of aviation personnel in the implementation of commercial passenger and cargo transport in the performance of unmanned and single pilot aircraft.

The social factor survey selected factors that may affect the implementation of the concept in passenger and cargo operations, as well as in unmanned and single-pilot flights - Table 1.

Table 1. Types of social factors

Lp.	Type of factor	Without the presence of a pilot	With the presence of 1 pilot
Passenger transport			
1.	Interest in flights	58% reduce interest	58% ill have no impact
2.	Discontent among airline industry groups	88% will arouse discontent	81% will arouse discontent
3.	Increase in employment of surveillance and traffic control personnel	46% increase employment	35% will reduce employment

4.	Flight organization	42% improve flight conditions	42% will worsen flight conditions
5.	Natural environment	65% - has no effect	77% has no effect
Freight shipments			
1.	Interest in transportation	65% It will not affect	62% will not affect
2.	Discontent among aviation industry groups - will worsen working conditions	77% will arouse discontent	77% will arouse discontent
3.	Increase in employment of surveillance and traffic control personnel	38% will not increase employment	35% - will reduce employment
4.	Flight arrangements	42% has no effect	46% has no effect
5.	Natural environment	65% has no effect	73% has no effect

Source: authors study

Liability and insurance

Fig. 14. Liability and insurance

Source: <https://www.pansa.pl/pansautm/>, access: 15.06.2024.

The system will consist of many users, technology providers and operators. At the same time, it will include more and more units in built-up areas over time. Mission security is a critical topic that requires strong attention. We must carefully analyze issues related to the liability of specific system participants and third parties. We need to consider the consequences of damaged packages or accidents involving drones. We need to consider the issue of compulsory and voluntary insurance and their scope.

Drone liability and insurance are crucial aspects of responsible unmanned aerial system (UAS) operation, addressing the risks associated with drone flights. Understanding and managing these risks through appropriate insurance is important for both commercial and recreational drone operators. Operating a drone carries potential risks, including property damage, personal injury, and privacy infringement. This liability can extend to accidents involving third parties, damage to property, and even data protection violations in the case of capturing unauthorized photographs or videos.

The insurance requirements may differ based on the drone's use. Commercial operators generally face higher risks due to the nature of their operations, making comprehensive insurance coverage more critical. In many regulations, commercial drone operators are required to have liability insurance. While this may not be mandatory for recreational users, it is still highly recommended to protect against potential claims.

Insurance policies might also offer coverage for breaches of privacy and data protection laws, which is particularly relevant in cases where drones collect and store data.

Drone liability and insurance are essential for managing the inherent risks in drone operations. They provide a safety net for operators and protect against potential financial losses, legal challenges, and claims. Whether for hobbyists or commercial users, understanding and obtaining the right insurance coverage is a key step in responsible drone operation.

Conclusions

The pace of urbanization development and the growth of the population create the need for cooperation with new technologies. Part of the problem is urban delivery and demand for this is likely to increase as e-commerce volumes grow. According to insurance company Swiss Re, the global urban population "... will increase by about 1.4 billion to 5 billion between 2011 and 2030, with a 90% increase in emerging markets ..." (Swiss Re's latest sigma). This data mobilizes the market to look for ideas to unload congested cities and use drones to deliver parcels. Courier deliveries in different countries are tested. The result of the delivered deliveries via the first intelligent route is the reduction of time from 40 to 8 minutes and a significant reduction in transport costs, with lower CO2 emissions and energy consumption. Various companies, small and large, compete in the field of cargo and courier services, embarking on various projects and tests. These works indicated many directions and opportunities for development, for example the supply of blood or organs using unmanned aerial vehicles. Unfortunately, technological possibilities alone are not enough, and at the same time, society must be prepared and educated in the field of airspace use.

The safe integration of crewed and unmanned aviation in the Polish sky is a complex but essential endeavor, aligning with the broader European Union aviation standards and the guidelines of the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA). It involves a comprehensive regulatory framework that caters to both traditional and emerging aviation technologies.

Central to this integration is the modernization of Air Traffic Management (ATM) systems, incorporating U-space services – a set of services and procedures designed to manage drone traffic and ensure safe operations in the airspace (Guillermet F. 2018).

Advanced technology plays a pivotal role, especially detect-and-avoid systems for drones, ensuring they can operate without posing risks to crewed aircraft. Real-time tracking and monitoring systems, along with geofencing, are vital for maintaining controlled airspace and preventing unauthorized drone activities near critical areas like airports (Balcerzak T., Kostur-Balcerzak K., Żmigrodzka M., 2019).

Education and training are equally important. This includes specialized training for drone operators in navigation, safety protocols, and compliance with aviation regulations. Pilots of crewed aircraft also need training to understand the dynamics of shared airspace with unmanned systems.

Public awareness campaigns are crucial for educating society about the safe and responsible use of drones, highlighting the legal and safety aspects. Furthermore, incident reporting and analysis systems are necessary for continual safety improvements, providing insights into potential risks and the effectiveness of current measures (Kostur K., Żmigrodzka M., Balcerzak T. 2020).

International collaboration is key, ensuring that Poland's approach is in line with global standards and best practices. This involves sharing knowledge, participating in joint research, and adopting innovations that enhance the safety and efficiency of integrated airspace operations.

Through these multi-dimensional efforts, Poland aims to create a balanced, safe, and efficient airspace environment, accommodating the rapid growth of unmanned aviation while upholding the highest safety standards in crewed aviation.

References:

1. Analiza prawnych aspektów polskiego sektora dronowego w ramach programu 2020 „Żwirko i Wigura”, Instytut im. Mikołaja Sienieckiego, 35-49 s.
2. Aomar, H., Bentley, P.J. (2021) Autonomous flight cycles and extreme landings of airliners beyond the current limits and capabilities using artificial neural networks. *Applied Intelligence*, 51:6349–6375 [https://doi.org/10.1007/s10489-021-02202-y]
3. Automation and innovations in logistic processes of electronic commerce [on-line cit: (?2022). Available from: https://www.swissre.com/media/press-release/2013/nr_20131031_sigma_urbanisation.html

4. Balcerzak T., Fellner R.(2016), Innovation of airports and aerodromes in transport policy of the European Union, Sci. J. Sil. Univ. Technol., Ser. Transp. 2016 vol. 90, s. 7-15, bibliogr. 31 poz.
5. Balcerzak T., Kostur-Balcerzak K., Żmigrodzka M., (2019), Cybersecurity in civil aviation, Bezpieczeństwo w międzynarodowym i krajowym prawie lotniczym i kosmicznym, ISBN: 978-83-7996-752-0
6. Balcerzak T.(2014), The safety of passengers, aircraft and infrastructure against current threats-solutions and technologies, [w.:] "Revista Europea De Derecho De La Navegacion Maritimay Aeronautica", Barcelona.
7. Balcerzak T.(2016), The airline industry in 2050, w: Problemy Transportu i Logistyki nr 1/2016 (33), (dawne Zeszyty Naukowe Uniwersytetu Szczecińskiego Problemy Transportu i Logistyki), ISSN 1644-275X, Wydawnictwo Naukowe Uniwersytetu Szczecińskiego, Szczecin.
8. Balcerzak T.(2017) What are the risks associated with today's ever-increasing air traffic in the world? [w.:] "Revista Europea De Derecho De La Navegacion Maritimay Aeronautica", ISSN (versión electrónica): 2386-8902, ISSN (versión impresa): 1130-2127 Depósito legal: Z-3235-99, Malaga 2017;
9. Cobel-Tokarska, (2011) „Przestrzeń społeczna. Krótkie wykłady z socjologii”
10. Feltynowski M. (2019), Wykorzystanie bezzałogowych platform powietrznych
11. Guillermet F. ?(2018), SESAR JU, European ATM Master Plan: Roadmap for the safe integration of drones into all classes of airspace, 19-29 p.
12. IAEA International Atomic Energy Agency, " Safety culture in nuclear installations, Guidance for use in the enhancement of safety culture" Grudzień 2002, Wiedeń
13. Kostur K., Żmigrodzka M., Balcerzak T.(2020), Bezzałogowe statki powietrzne w ochronie przeciwpożarowej, Unmanned aerial vehicles in fire protection, REVISTA EUROPEA DE DERECHO DE LA NAVIGACIÓN MARÍTIMA YAERONÁUTICA, ISSN (versión electrónica): 2386-8902, ISSN (versión impresa): 1130-2127 Depósito legal: Z-3235-99 Malaga.
14. Niklas J., Walkowiak A. (2014) (oprac.),Raporty Fundacji Panoptykon, Drony – nadzór z powietrza oraz Zabawki Wielkiego Brata, 6-8 s.
15. PansaUTM <https://www.pansa.pl/en/u-space/>
16. Pyzynski M., Balcerzak T. (2020),Cybersecurity of the Unmanned Aircraft System (UAS), REVISTA EUROPEA DE DERECHO DE LA NAVIGACIÓN MARÍTIMA YAERONÁUTICA, ISSN (versión electrónica): 2386-8902, ISSN (versión impresa): 1130-2127 Depósito legal: Z-3235-99 Malaga.
17. Raport(2022): „Analiza czynników społecznych, bezpieczeństwa, technologii, prawa oraz ekonomii w kontekście możliwości redukcji personelu lotniczego w realizacji komercyjnych przewozów pasażerskich oraz cargo przy wykorzystaniu bezzałogowych statków powietrznych oraz z załogą jednoosobową w aspekcie oferowanych przez system szkolnictwa kwalifikacji lotniczych w odniesieniu do potrzeb pracodawców”, <http://rada-przemyslu-lotkos.pl/raporty-z-badan> .
18. Stanley M., (2019). Are Flying Cars Preparing for Takeoff, [<https://www.morganstanley.com/ideas/autonomous-aircraft>]

19. Swiss Re's latest sigma study addresses the challenges and opportunities of urbanization in emerging markets for insurers, [on-line cit: 2022.06.23]. Available from: https://www.swissre.com/media/press-release/2013/nr_20131031_sigma_urbanisation.html
w operacjach na rzecz bezpieczeństwa publicznego, CNOP - PIB, Józefów., 46-48 s. (in Polish).
20. Xiao-Guang Yang, Teng Liu, Shanhai Ge, Eric Rountree, Chao-Yang Wang,(2021) Challenges and key requirements of batteries for electric vertical takeoff and landing aircraft, Joule, Volume 5(7),1644-1659, [<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2021.05.001>]
21. Żmigrodzka M.(2022) *Opportunities and Threats to Services using Unmanned Aerial Systems*, Humanities & Social Sciences Reviews, eISSN2395-6518.